

iMERMAID Project: Integrating Satellite and In-Situ Data for Water Pollution Identification in the Mediterranean basin

Shelestov A.^{1,2}, Drozd S.^{1,2}, Yailymov B.², Henitsoi P.¹, Donate J.³, Milián M.³, Rostan J.³, Sedano R.³

¹ National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky KPI"

² Space Research Institute of NAS of Ukraine and SSA of Ukraine

³ ITCL Technology Center of Spain "Instituto Tecnológico de Castilla y León"

Context and Research Objectives

The study presents **satellite data** and **AI** as an innovative alternative to the limited traditional methods for **monitoring chemical pollution** in the Mediterranean Sea, aiming to:

- Develop satellite-based methods for monitoring water quality (chlorophyll-a, turbidity).
- Enhance the spatial resolution of global satellite products (MODIS, GCOM-C) using machine learning models to improve consistency with in-situ measurements.
- Investigate the relationship between anthropogenic activities and water pollution.
- Assess the potential of PRISMA hyperspectral imagery for pollutant detection.

Methods

1) **Correlation analysis** between satellite data and in-situ measurements

2) Calculating the **Normalized Difference Chlorophyll Index**

$$NDCI = \frac{B5 - B4}{B5 + B4}$$

3) **MLP and RF regression models** to estimate CHL-a using Sentinel-2 satellite and in-situ Coriolis data.

4) **LR and RF for downscaling** of Aqua MODIS and GCOM-C CHL-a (4km → 300 m)

Data used

Satellite data:

- 1) Sentinel-2 (10m)
- 2) Sentinel-3 (300m)
- 3) Aqua MODIS (4 km)
- 4) GCOM-c (4 km)

In-situ measurements

- (at depths of 0-10 m):
- 1) Coriolis
 - 2) SeaDataNet CDI

Results

Correlations between in-situ data with the GCOM-C

Sample Number	Depth (m)	R ²	Corr.
377	5	0.35	0.59
466	10	0.30	0.54
600	20	0.32	0.57
886	50	0.18	0.43
1569	All	0.01	0.11

Results of CHL-a prediction using Sentinel-2

Aqua MODIS and GCOM-C downscaling

Aqua MODIS:
R² = 0.74,
RMSE = 0.006 (LR, RF)

GCOM-C:
R² = 0.60,
RMSE = 0.008 (RF)

Hyperspectral detection

1) **Hyperspectral data** from PRISMA with **236 bands** (400-2500 nm) and 30m resolution

2) **Sentinel-2 data** resampled from originally 4km to 30m

3) **Geospatial rescaling of hyperspectral coordinates** using interpolation techniques to match the pollutant data grid

4) Tested different models, from classic regression to neural networks

5) **Tested preprocessing:** MSC, SNV, Svitzky-Golay derivatives, PCA. Did not improve the result

6) Implemented a **feedforward neural network** with **two hidden layers** (128 and 64 neurons, ReLU activations), trained with Adam optimizer and MSE loss for regression

The results of the PRISMA correlation shows a R² of 0.7648

Traffic & Pollutants

1) Identified **zones of high, medium, and low density**

2) Research for relationship between maritime density and pollutant levels

3) Pollutant considered: **Volume absorption coefficient of radiative flux in sea water** due to dissolved organic matter and non algal particles

4) **Kruskal-Wallis test** applied to compare zones with high density with zones with low density.

5) **Results** determined a **p** significantly under 0.05 between groups

References

1. P. Henitsoi, A. Shelestov. Transfer Learning Model for Chlorophyll-a Estimation Using Satellite Imagery. 4th International Symposium on Applied Geoinformatics (ISAG2024), May 9 – 10, 2024, 15247. <https://www.kongresistemi.com/panel/UserUploads/Files/a3fe58047d50fbc.pdf>
2. B. Yailymov, P. Henitsoi, N. Kussul, A. Shelestov Increasing Chlorophyll-A Spatial Resolution Using Machine Learning. IEEE International Conference on System Analysis & Intelligent Computing (SAIC), October 08 – 11, 2024
3. B. Yailymov, N. Kussul, P. Henitsoi, A. Shelestov Improving spatial resolution of chlorophyll-a in the Mediterranean sea based on machine learning. Journal Radioelectronic and Computer Systems. Vol 2024, No 2 (2024), p. 52-65. <https://doi.org/10.32620/reks.2024.2.05>
4. S. Drozd, N. Kussul Downscaling Aqua MODIS and GCOM-C Data for Enhanced Chlorophyll-a Monitoring in Cyprus' Coastal Waters with Sentinel-3 and Machine Learning. European Journal of Remote Sensing (on reviewing).
5. H. Wu, W. Li, Downscaling land surface temperatures using a random forest regression model with multitype predictor variables, IEEE Access 7 (2019) 21904-21916. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2896241>.
6. J. Peng, A. Loew, O. Merlin, N.E. Verhoest, A review of spatial downscaling of satellite remotely sensed soil moisture, Reviews of Geophysics 55 (2017) 341-366. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016RG000543>
7. Amieva, Juan Francisco, Daniele Oxoli, and Maria Antonia Brovelli. "Machine and Deep Learning Regression of Chlorophyll-a Concentrations in Lakes Using PRISMA Satellite Hyperspectral Imagery." Remote Sensing 15.22 (2023): 5385. <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/15/22/5385>